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Review of “Comparison of the Von Kármán and Kirchhoff models for the post-buckling and vibrations of elastic beams”

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1 Reviewer (Y. Vetyukov)

Reviewer

The authors carefully consider the implications of the conventional approach to treat moderate geometrically nonlinear behavior of straight beams. This model, which is frequently used in practice, is attributed by the authors to S. Woinowsky-Krieger. Comparing solutions, predicted by this model to the geometrically exact solutions for Kirchhoff beams, the authors demonstrate the limitations of the WK model and accurately estimate its range of applicability. The direct simulation results are supported by the asymptotic analysis of the exact nonlinear equations. Moreover, the authors suggest another 3rd order model, which is simpler than the fully nonlinear one, but which is capable of describing effects, not captured by the WK model. The scientific novelty of the contribution is undoubtful, the quality of presentation is high, and the manuscript clearly deserves to be published. Minor comments below do not impact the overall quality of the contribution.

2 Editor’s comments (A. Popp)

Three independent reviews by expert referees have been provided for the given paper, all of which evaluated the contribution extremely positively asides a few minor comments. These minor remarks have been thoroughly addressed by the authors within a revised version of the manuscript. Only one of the three reviews is printed here, since the two other reviewers advised the handling editor to keep their review remarks confidential.